

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DETERMINATION OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS IN THE NORTH MACEDONIA

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ABSTRACT

Dental fluorosis is caused by excessive fluorine intake during tooth development.

Aim

The aim of this study is to assess the prevalence of dental fluorosis among children in the Republic of North Macedonia.

Method

The investigation was conducted on a group of 1,591 school children, aged 6, 12, and 15 years, of both genders. Among the participants, 313 (19.67%) were 6 years old, 641 (40.29%) were 12 years old, and 637 (40.04%) were 15 years old. The dental fluorosis status of the participants was evaluated using the 2013 World Health Organization diagnostic criteria. Initially, the frontal permanent teeth were clinically examined, and if suspicious changes were detected, the permanent molars were also examined. Any participant exhibiting any degree of dental fluorosis was photographed using a Sony Cyber-shot DSC-P73 digital camera. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), version 20, was used for data management and analysis. Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare the difference between the concentration of fluorine in drinking water and the severity of dental fluorosis. Statistical significance for all statistical procedures was set at ≤ 0.05 .

Results:

Dental fluorosis of the first, second, and third degree was observed in 51 children who had been lifelong residents of settlements with higher concentrations of fluoride in drinking water. Five of these children, aged 6, were from the villages of Monospitovo and Gradsko. Forty children, aged 12, were from the villages of Monospitovo, Viničani, and Gradsko, and 6 children, aged 15, were from the village of Viničani.

Conclusion:

Dental fluorosis among children in the Republic of North Macedonia has a low prevalence.

Keywords: dental fluorosis, schoolchildren, fluoride.

Introduction

Drinking fluoridated water and exposure to excessive amounts of fluoride from toothpaste and supplements in preschool children increase the risk of dental fluorosis. Mild and very mild dental fluorosis do not have as significant an impact on children's quality of life and dental aesthetics as moderate and severe forms of dental fluorosis (1).

The prevalence of dental fluorosis was high in North Macedonia in the past. It varies across and within regions, primarily due to regional differences in fluoride exposure. Three endemic fluorotic regions were identified: the Northeast, Vardar, and Pelagonia regions, including villages near the cities of Kumanovo, Veles, and Prilep (21).

Currently, we know that the anti-caries effect of fluoridated water is primarily due to its presence in the oral cavity before it is ingested. However, the total amount of fluoride that enters the body remains a subject of interest for dentists. The optimal daily fluoride consumption from various sources should fall within the range of 0.5 to 0.7 mg/kg of body weight (3).

Some studies have established that a fluoride concentration of 0.8-1.5 mg/L in drinking water can reduce dental caries by more than 60% (4, 5). Individuals and groups of low socio-economic status consistently benefit more from fluoridated water than those of higher socio-economic status (6-8). These findings suggest that fluoridated water can be a powerful tool for reducing inequalities in the oral health status of the entire population.

Extensive research has demonstrated that high concentrations of fluoride negatively affect ameloblasts by impairing their cellular functions, reducing protein synthesis and secretion, and hindering cell cycle progression (9). Additionally, fluoride induces oxidative stress and damages DNA (10).

Various WHO special committees have repeatedly re-examined all relevant data, including epidemiological data on fluorosis, caries prevalence, and climatic conditions, leading to the issuance of several guidelines over the past 40 years (WHA, 1975, 1978; WHO, 1971, 1984, 1993, 2003) (11-15).

The Republic of North Macedonia (RSM) is located on the Balkan Peninsula in South-eastern Europe, and it is one of the successor states of the former Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (SFRY), from which it declared independence in 1991. The country covers approximately 38% of the total area of the historical Macedonia region. Geographically, it borders Serbia to the north, Kosovo to the northwest, Bulgaria to the east, Greece to the south, and Albania to the west. The country's terrain is predominantly mountainous. Although landlocked, it is home to over 50 lakes and 16 mountains above 2,000 meters.

Most of the population of the Republic of North Macedonia is supplied with drinking water from underground sources and karst springs (e.g., Skopje, Tetovo, Gostivar, Debar, Struga, Ohrid, Prilep, Kichevo). The second-largest source is surface water, serving cities like Bitola, Kumanovo, Strumica, Veles, Berovo, Vinica, and St. Nikole. Third, settlements using underground water foundations include Stip, Kočani, Gevgelija, Delčevo, and Radovish. A small number of residents in villages on Suva Gora rely on stormwater (16).

Drinking water in the Republic, especially in larger cities, typically has fluoride concentrations lower than 0.2 mg/L (17-20). The study aimed to determine the prevalence of dental fluorosis in children from the Republic of North Macedonia.

Material and Methods

Ethical approval was obtained from the Faculty of Dental Medicine, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, Skopje, North Macedonia (N #06-153218) prior to the initiation of the study. The study was conducted in three regions of the Republic of North Macedonia: Vardar, Eastern, and South-eastern.

Participants

Participation in the study was completely voluntary. *In the Republic of North Macedonia, an average of 180,627 children are enrolled per generation. With a 5% margin of error, a 90% confidence level, and an assumed response distribution of 50%, the minimum required sample size is 271 per surveyed generation.* The final study population consisted of 1 591 school children aged 6 (n = 313), 12 (n = 641) and 15 years (n = 637). The dental fluorosis status of the participants was assessed using the World Health Organization diagnostic criteria (2013) (21).

Inclusion criteria were children aged 6, 12, and 15 years, born and raised in the selected region to assess long-term exposure to local environmental factors,

with no systemic diseases or special needs, and with the willingness of both the child and their parents or legal guardians to participate in the study, confirmed by written informed consent.

Data collection

Dean's index was used to assess the presence and severity of dental fluorosis (22). All examinations were conducted in natural daylight while the children were seated on ordinary chairs in their classrooms. The permanent upper teeth were dried with gauze before being visually inspected using a disposable mouth mirror and explorer. Two trained and calibrated dentists conducted all clinical examinations. Training sessions were held at the Faculty of Dental Medicine, University Ss. Cyril & Methodius, Skopje, where Dean's index and its categories were discussed using photographs. Kappa coefficients ranged from 0.91 to 0.97 for inter-examiner and intra-examiner reliability.

For all 6-, 12-, and 15-year-old schoolchildren, standard dental systematic examinations were conducted and recorded using the WHO Oral Health Assessment Form (1997) (21).

In the WHO form, data on the possible presence of fluorosis on the permanent teeth is recorded. First, the frontal permanent teeth are examined, and if suspicious changes are found, the permanent molars are also examined. The following legend is used to describe the degree of dental fluorosis: 0 = No dental fluorosis; 1 = Suspected dental fluorosis; 2 = Very mild dental fluorosis; 3 = Mild dental fluorosis; 4 = Moderately expressed dental fluorosis; 5 = Strongly expressed dental fluorosis and 6 = Extremely expressed dental fluorosis.

First, the frontal permanent teeth were clinically examined, and if suspicious changes were detected, the permanent molars were also clinically investigated. Every patient with any degree of dental fluorosis was recorded using a Sony Cyber-shot DSC-P73 (Sony, Tokyo, Japan) digital camera.

Data analysis

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20, (IBM Corp, Armonk, New York, USA), was used for data management and analysis. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize sample characteristics and the distribution of dental fluorosis. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare differences in the concentration of fluoride in drinking water and the severity of dental fluorosis. Statistical significance for all tests was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Result

The study sample comprised a slightly higher proportion of boys (53.01%) than girls.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the analysed children at ages 6, 12, and 15 in relation to the degree of detected fluorosis. As seen from the results, dental fluorosis was most frequently observed in children aged 12 (2.34%). However, this group also had the highest percentage of suspected fluorosis (2.96%). According to the results of the chi-square test, no statistically significant difference in the prevalence of dental fluorosis was found among six-year-olds ($p = 0.862$), twelve-year-olds ($p = 0.845$), and fifteen-year-olds ($p = 0.991$).

Table 1.

Degree of dental fluorosis	Age of respondents		
	6 year (n=313)	12 year (n=641)	15 year (n=637)
0 – without dental fluorosis	308 (98.40%)	601 (93.76%)	631 (98.9%)
1 – suspected of dental fluorosis	2 (0.64%)	23 (3.59%)	6 (1.1%)
2 – very mild dental fluorosis	3 (0.96%)	8 (1.25%)	0 (0%)
3 – mild dental fluorosis	0 (0%)	9 (1.40%)	0 (0%)

Table 2 shows the concentration of Fluoride in Water according to the Degree of Dental Fluorosis in Children Aged 6, 12, and 15 Years. In the group of 6-year-old children, the average fluoride concentration in water, in relation to the degree of fluorosis, ranges from 0.23 ± 0.22 in the group without fluorosis to 0.86 in the groups with suspected and very mild dental fluorosis. ANOVA analysis revealed a statistically significant difference between the groups ($F = 19.729$, $p \leq 0.001$). The post hoc test identified a significant difference between groups without dental fluorosis and suspected dental fluorosis ($p \leq 0.001$) and between without dental fluorosis and very mild dental fluorosis ($p \leq 0.001$).

In the group of 12-year-old children, the average fluoride concentration in water, in relation to the degree of fluorosis, ranges from 0.45 ± 0.42 in the group without fluorosis to 2.32 in the group with very mild fluorosis and 1.53 ± 1.09 in the group with mild fluorosis).

ANOVA analysis confirmed a highly significant difference in fluoride concentration depending on the degree of fluorosis ($F = 50.567$, $p \leq 0.001$). The post hoc test revealed a significant difference between the group without dental fluorosis and those with suspected dental fluorosis ($p \leq 0.001$), very mild dental fluorosis ($p \leq 0.001$), and mild dental fluorosis ($p \leq 0.001$). Additionally, a significant difference was found between the groups with suspected dental fluorosis and very mild dental fluorosis ($p \leq 0.001$).

In the group of 15-year-old children, the average fluoride concentration in water, in relation to the degree of fluorosis, ranges from 0.3 ± 0.2 in the group without fluorosis to 1.86 ± 0.72 in the group with suspected fluorosis. An independent t-test identified a significant difference between group without dental fluorosis and suspected dental fluorosis ($t = -17.559$, $p \leq 0.001$).

Table 2.

Concentration of Fluoride in Water and Degree of Dental Fluorosis in Children Aged 6, 12, and 15 Years

Degree of dental fluorosis	Concentration of fluorine in water		
	mean \pm SD		
	6-year-olds (n=313)	12 year-olds (n=641)	15- year-olds (n=637)
	Mean value \pm standard deviation	Mean value \pm standard deviation	Mean value \pm standard deviation
0 – without dental fluorosis	n=308 0.23 ± 0.22	n=601 0.45 ± 0.42	n=631 0.3 ± 0.2
1 – suspected of dental fluorosis	n=2 0.86 ± 0.00	n=23 1.16 ± 1.00	n=6 1.86 ± 0.72
2 – very mild dental fluorosis	n=3 0.86 ± 0.00	n=8 2.32 ± 0.00	-
3 – mild dental fluorosis	-	n=9 1.53 ± 1.09	-

Discussion

In the past, there were three endemic fluorotic areas in the Republic of Macedonia: near the city of Kumanovo in the Northeast region, near the city of Veles in the Vardar region, and near the city of Prilep in the Pelagonia region. Carčev et al. (1992) (20) conducted research in which they determined the relationship between fluoride in drinking water and caries frequency in endemic areas compared to other control settlements. Near Kumanovo, which includes the villages of Tromeđe, Ajdučka Česma, Pukovsko, and Beli Gramadi, the mean fluoride concentration in drinking water from wells was 2.75 mg/L, while from taps it was 1.48 mg/L. In the control settlement (Staro Nagoričane), the fluoride concentration was 0.20 mg/L. In the vicinity of Veles, specifically in the village of Vinichani, the average DMFT index ranged from 0.79 to 1.92 , while in the control settlement (Gradsko), it was 5.92 . The fluoride concentration in drinking water from

all sources in this area was 1.24 mg/L, while in the control settlement, it was 0.58 mg/L. The average DMFT index in this area was 2.30 , compared to 6.24 in the control settlement. In the vicinity of Prilep, in the village of Novo Lagovo, the mean fluoride concentration in drinking water was 1.93 mg/L in October 1985 and 1.60 mg/L in June 1986. In the control settlement (village Berovci), the fluoride concentration was 0.20 mg/L. The average DMFT index in this endemic area was 2.10 , compared to 3.83 in the control settlement (20). From our current research, it can be noted that such fluorotic zones in our country no longer exist. This is due to the fact that even in the villages people no longer drink water from wells.

Gjorgjev et al. performed a systematic examination of the basic parameters of nutritional and dental status (dental caries and dental fluorosis) in 76 school-children. In some of the examined children (test group), who had been drinking water with an average fluoride

content of 2.71 mg/L since birth (Tromede village), the average DMFT index of the permanent teeth was very low, amounting to 0.56. However, most of them exhibited fluorosis between I and II degree ("mild" and "very mild"). In contrast, in the control group, who had been drinking water with less than 0.5 mg/L of fluoride (village Staro Nagoričane), the average DMFT index was 3.09, and dental fluorosis was absent. No significant differences in nutritional status between the two groups were found (5).

Currently, in the village of Tromede, the fluoride content in drinking water has been optimized to about 1 mg/L, thanks to the mixing of water from the newly built village water supply with water from the Kumanovo city water supply, which contains approximately 0.1-0.2 mg/L of fluoride. Research by numerous authors has shown that fluoride concentrations in drinking water between 0.8 and 1.5 mg/L can result in a reduction of dental caries by more than 60% (2, 5, 23).

In their research Kolevska et al found the highest mean values of fluorine in the underground waters in Pelagonia, Ovchepolieto, Povardarjeto and in some spring waters of Belasica and Osogovo. She mentions that in the largest number of these cases, it is about very small springs intended for water supply to settlements that are in decline and with an unfavorable age structure, that is, a reduced number of children. These are the villages in the municipalities of Veles, Negotino, Prilep, Bitola, Kratovo, Kriva Palanka, Sveti Nikole, Shtip and Probishtip. The municipalities in which the villages show demographic expansion with a large number of children are mostly located in localities where there are water sources that contain, mainly, small amounts of fluoride. These are the waters from the sources of Shar Planina, Suva Gora, Buković, Korab-Deshat, Skopje Montenegro, Jablanica (5). In the eastern part of our country and partly in the underground waters in Povardarje, Ovchepolije and next to Bregalnica, somewhat higher values are found, which are close to the optimal, and in waters where, as a rule, the mineralization of water is also higher. Natural sources containing fluorine, as a rule, are of low or completely low capacity. These sources are mainly located in eastern Macedonia, where there is a triangle with a geological composition of erupted rocks and where a significant number of the tested waters have a concentration close to the optimum (the municipalities of Kumanovo, Kočani, Shtip, Radovish, Strumica and St. Nikole) (5).

Armfield JM in his study conducted in Australia, included 128,900 children aged 5-15 years and made a comparison between caries prevalence and average DMFT index among children living since birth in areas with insignificant concentration of fluoride in water (<0.3 ppm) and those who live in areas with an optimal concentration of fluoride in water (≥ 0.7). The average DMFT index was 28.7% higher in primary and 31.6% in permanent dentition in children who lived in areas with low compared to children who lived in areas with optimal concentration of fluoride in the water from their birth (24).

In the meta-analysis (York review) of older data from the registration of fluorosis in areas with 1 mg

F/L, Treasure ET et al found that 48% of the examined children developed fluorosis, while 12.5% of them had an aesthetic problem. Conversely, in areas with 0.1 mg F/L, the prevalence of fluorosis was 15%, while 6% of fluorosis cases had an aesthetic problem (25).

The general conclusion of all fluorosis research conducted is that, despite the variety of values, mild fluorosis has been increasing in recent years and that such a finding is attributable to an increase in total fluoride intake from sources other than water. In Australia, the reduction of the concentration of fluoride in drinking water has led to a reduction in the prevalence of fluorosis and, of course, the measure to re-regulate the upper limit of fluoride in water is considered a factor that prevented the appearance of hypoplastic tooth enamel caused by excess fluoride, that is, fluorosis (26).

The relationship between the dose of fluoride and the symptoms of fluorosis is linear. This means that for every increase in the dose by 0.01 mg F/kg bw, an increase in dental fluorosis is expected at the population level. The severity of fluorosis is roughly proportional to the following factors (27):

- from the age of the child at the beginning of his exposure to a larger amount of fluoride. In essence, the impact depends on the stage in which the tooth enamel is in the process of its formation at the moment when its exposure to a larger amount of fluoride begins;

- from the duration of the child's exposure to a high concentration of fluoride. It refers to what stage of tooth formation and calcification occurred during the period of increased exposure to fluoride; and

- from the total amount of fluoride that is taken in the critical (decisive) period of tooth calcification, i.e. in the first stage of tooth enamel maturation.

There are also some other factors related to the pharmacokinetics of fluoride in the body (absorption, secretion, allocation), which play a role in the severity of fluorosis, and they are:

1. the empty stomach, because the low pH is beneficial for the resorption of fluoride;

2. the presence of calcium or magnesium in the contents of the stomach, elements that have a beneficial effect on the binding of fluoride;

3. the type of diet of the individual (meat-eating, vegetarianism), which affects the secretion of fluoride; and

4. living at high altitude, a condition that generally changes the body's metabolism.

There are several indicators that measure the severity of fluorosis. The first indicator was introduced by Dean and, taking the mouth as a reference unit, uses a five-level scale (suspected fluorosis, very mild, mild, moderate and severe) and puts it in relation to the concentration of fluoride in the water. To determine the frequency of occurrence of fluorosis in the population, it introduces the Communal Fluorosis Index (Fci).

Thylstrup & Fejerskov in 1978 introduced a new index (TF index) and, taking the tooth as a reference unit, registers the degree of fluorosis in all teeth of the individual individually, since the severity of fluorosis appears unevenly distributed. Thylstrup & Fejerskov are the first to note that with constant exposure to

higher fluoride concentrations, teeth that erupt early (eg incisors and first molars) show the lightest degree of fluorosis, while teeth that erupt later (eg premolars, second molars) show the most severe degree of fluorosis. With this indicator, there is not one value per individual, but one value per tooth. The scale they introduced was of nine degrees (1-9) and they put it in relation to the histopathological findings of the sections of several teeth, independent of the concentration of fluoride in the water of the area from which the teeth were taken. The aesthetic problem for the patient is determined by the degree of fluorosis registered on the upper incisors. The level at which fluorosis is considered to cause a problem corresponds to the degree $TF \geq 3$, according to the Thylstrup & Fejerskov index. This degree of fluorosis corresponds to the degree of fluorosis of "mild" form according to the scale of Dean (28).

Indermitte E et al., in their study conducted in Estonia, found a strong correlation between the level of fluoride in natural drinking water and the prevalence of dental fluorosis. Most of the population living in the central and western parts of the country is exposed to higher concentrations of fluoride in drinking water. The risk of dental fluorosis among the population in Estonia occurs when the fluoride content in drinking water exceeds 1.5 mg/L (29).

Aminabadi N et al. conducted a fluorosis examination of 58 children aged 5 and 6 years and 421 children aged 7 to 12 years in the northwestern villages of Mako district, Iran. According to the Thylstrup & Fejerskov index, the highest concordance of the homologous teeth was observed in the mandibular incisors, while the lowest was observed in the maxillary second molars. The difference in fluorosis severity between the maxilla and mandible was statistically significant. Additionally, the severity of discoloration in maxillary central incisors increased with age (30).

Results from the survey conducted by Ambarkova et al. show that spring waters have a relatively low fluoride content. A higher content of fluorine they found in well water, while the fluorine content of surface water was also low. Waters originating from greater depths are richer in fluoride than those from shallower depths. Water with lower hardness also contains less fluoride, while hard water has a higher fluoride content. The content of fluorine in the water depends on the geological composition of the land with which the water comes into contact during its movement (17).

Water with a high concentration of fluoride is most commonly found in groundwater that is low in calcium and located in aquifers made of granites and gneisses, as well as in geothermal waters and some sedimentary basins. Groundwater with a high fluoride concentration is found in many regions of the world, including large parts of Africa, China, the Eastern Mediterranean, and South Asia (India, Sri Lanka). One of the most well-known terrestrial high-fluoride belts runs along the East African Rift, from Eritrea to Malawi. Another such belt stretches from Turkey through Iraq, Iran, Afghanistan, India, and into the southern part of Thailand and China (31).

Larsen et al. conducted a study in Denmark examining dental fluorosis among 456 children aged 14–16 years who had permanent residence since birth in four Danish regions with varying fluoride concentrations in drinking water (32). The presence and severity of fluorosis were assessed using the Thylstrup and Fejerskov classification system. The children were divided into four groups based on the fluoride concentration in their drinking water: less than 0.1 ppm, 0.3–0.5 ppm, 0.5–1.25 ppm, and 1.26–2.0 ppm. The results demonstrated that the later a tooth forms during childhood, the higher the prevalence of dental fluorosis. According to the authors of the mentioned study, the concentration of fluoride in drinking water influences the prevalence of fluorosis on all teeth except the lower incisors, which are formed very early in life while for all other teeth, the prevalence of the condition increases proportionally with higher fluoride concentrations in water, with a similar trend across different types of teeth. However, the greatest increase in both prevalence and severity was observed in teeth that form later during childhood. The authors suggest that these findings reflect water consumption habits within the population as well as the use of fluoride prophylaxis (32).

Brothwell D and Limeback H, in their 2003 study, confirmed that prolonged use of artificial milk substitutes increases the risk of fluorosis, a phenomenon not observed in children fed with breast milk (33).

Parents who use bottled water to prepare their baby's milk should be aware that if it contains high concentrations of fluoride, they are exposing their child to the risk of dental fluorosis (34).

This study has certain limitations. Although fluoride concentration in drinking water was measured, no questionnaire was used to collect data on other potential sources of fluoride intake, such as dietary habits or the use of fluoridated toothpaste. The study included only three regions (Vardar, Eastern, and South-Eastern), which limits the generalizability of the findings to the entire country. While Dean's Index is a standardized tool, it relies on visual assessment and is subject to examiner interpretation, which may affect the accuracy of fluorosis severity estimation. Furthermore, clinical examinations were conducted in school classrooms under natural light and on regular chairs, which does not provide an optimal diagnostic environment.

This study has significant implications for oral health services, planning, and education in North Macedonia. The results indicate a low prevalence of dental fluorosis, affecting only 3.21 % of the study population. The affected children exhibited either very mild or mild forms of dental fluorosis, or were suspected of having dental fluorosis. With the introduction of new water supply systems in endemic areas of northern Macedonia and the decreasing reliance on wells in rural areas, it can be concluded that dental fluorosis has effectively been eradicated within the population.

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Conflict of interest

None disclosed

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